

Supplementary information

Sup data Table 1: Plant species observations

Sr. No.	Type	Plant Name	Scientific Name	Growth Form
1	Mangrove	Holly Mangrove	Acanthus ilicifolius	Mangrove
2	Mangrove	Grey Mangrove	Avicennia marina	Mangrove
3	Mangrove	Indian Mangrove	Avicennia officinalis	Mangrove
4	Mangrove	Apple Mangrove	Sonneratia alba	Mangrove
5	Mangrove	Sonneratia Mangrove	Sonneratia apetala	Mangrove
6	Mangrove Associated	Rosary pea	Abrus precatorius	Climbers
14	Mangrove Associated	Babul	Acacia nilotica	Trees
11	Mangrove Associated	Indian Caper	Capparis sepiaria	Shrubs
7	Mangrove Associated	Common derris	Derris trifoliata	Climbers
8	Mangrove Associated	Velvet Bean	Mucuna pruriens	Climbers
9	Mangrove Associated	Turpeth	Operculina turpethum	Climbers
12	Mangrove Associated	Toothbrush tree	Salvadora persica	Shrubs
10	Mangrove Associated	Jukti	Stephanotis volubilis	Climbers
15	Mangrove Associated	Portia Tree	Thespesia populnea	Trees
13	Mangrove Associated	Five-leaved Chaste Tree	Vitex negundo	Shrubs
45	Other	Wild okra	Abelmoschus esculentus	Shrubs
58	Other	Indian bael	Aegle marmelos	Trees
30	Other	White Moneywort	Alysicarpus vaginalis	Herbs
59	Other	Neem	Azadirachta indica	Trees
26	Other	Golden Bamboo	Bambusa vulgaris	Grasses
60	Other	Bidi Leaf Tree	Bauhinia racemosa	Trees
61	Other	Orchid Tree	Bauhinia variegata	Trees
31	Other	Wineflower	Boerhavia diffusa	Herbs
62	Other	Red Silk Cotton Tree	Bombax ceiba	Trees
63	Other	Flame of the Forest	Butea monosperma	Trees
46	Other	Pigeon Pea	Cajanus cajan	Shrubs
27	Other	Crown Flower	Calotropis gigantea	Grasses
64	Other	Golden Shower Tree	Cassia fistula	Trees
47	Other	Stinking Cassia	Cassia tora	Shrubs
16	Other	Three-Leaved Wild Vine	Causonis trifolia	Climbers
65	Other	Kapok Tree	Ceiba pentandra	Trees
28	Other	Quail Grass	Celosia argentea	Grasses
48	Other	Asian Spiderflower	Cleome viscosa	Shrubs
17	Other	Blue Pea	Clitoria ternatea	Climbers
18	Other	Ivy Gourd	Coccinia grandis	Climbers
66	Other	Scarlet Cordia	Cordia sebestena	Trees
67	Other	Indian Rosewood	Dalbergia sissoo	Trees
68	Other	May-flower Tree	Delonix regia	Trees
32	Other	Creeping Dentella	Dentella repens	Herbs

33	Other	Samoan Clover	Desmodium scorpiurus	Herbs
34	Other	Asthma Plant	Euphorbia hirta	Herbs
69	Other	Indian Banyan	Ficus benghalensis	Trees
70	Other	Rubber Plant	Ficus elastica	Trees
71	Other	Cluster Fig	Ficus racemosa	Trees
72	Other	Sacred Fig	Ficus religiosa	Trees
49	Other	Flame Lily	Gloriosa superba	Shrubs
19	Other	Creeping Tick Trefoil	Grona triflora	Climbers
35	Other	Indian Heliotrope	Heliotropium indicum	Herbs
73	Other	Indian Elm	Holoptelea integrifolia	Trees
50	Other	Barbados Nut	Jatropha curcas	Shrubs
51	Other	Malabar Nut	Justicia adhatoda	Shrubs
74	Other	Sausage Tree	Kigelia africana	Trees
20	Other	Hyacinth Bean	Lablab purpureus	Climbers
75	Other	Giant Crepe-Myrtle	Lagerstroemia speciosa	Trees
52	Other	Hawaii Woodnettle	Laportea interrupta	Shrubs
53	Other	White Leadtree	Leucaena leucocephala	Shrubs
36	Other	Indian Lindenbergia	Lindenbergia indica	Herbs
21	Other	Sponge Gourd	Luffa aegyptiaca	Climbers
76	Other	Mahua	Madhuca longifolia	Trees
77	Other	Yellow Jade Orchid Tree	Magnolia champaca	Trees
54	Other	Malva de Caballo	Malachra capitata	Shrubs
78	Other	Indian mango	Mangifera indica	Trees
79	Other	Indian beach tree	Millettia pinnata	Trees
80	Other	Indian Beech Tree	Millettia pinnata	Trees
81	Other	Indian Cork Tree	Millingtonia hortensis	Trees
82	Other	Bakul tree	Mimusops elengi	Trees
83	Other	True Kadamb	Mitragyna parvifolia	Trees
22	Other	Teasle Gourd	Momordica dioica	Climbers
84	Other	Moringa Tree	Moringa oleifera	Trees
85	Other	Kadamba	Neolamarckia cadamba	Trees
37	Other	Old World Diamond Flower	Oldenlandia corymbosa	Herbs
86	Other	Ficus hispida	Opposite Leaf Fig	Trees
87	Other	Yellow flame tree	Peltophorum pterocarpum	Trees
38	Other	Turkey Tangle Frogfruit	Phyla nodiflora	Herbs
88	Other	Gale of the Wind	Phyllanthus acidus	Trees
39	Other	Bhuiavla	Phyllanthus amarus	Herbs
89	Other	Madras Thorn	Pithecellobium dulce	Trees
40	Other	Common Purslane	Portulaca oleracea	Herbs
90	Other	Kanak Champa	Pterospermum acerifolium	Trees
91	Other	Buddha Coconut	Pterygota alata	Trees
92	Other	Putranjiva	Putranjiva roxburghii	Trees
55	Other	Castor bean	Ricinus communis	Shrubs
93	Other	Kusum	Schleichera oleosa	Trees

94	Other	Kasod	Senna siamea	Trees
56	Other	Sesame	Sesamum indicum	Shrubs
29	Other	Johnsongrasses	Sorghum halepense	Grasses
41	Other	Nodeweed	Synedrella nodiflora	Herbs
23	Other	Blue Wiss	Teramnus labialis	Climbers
95	Other	Jungli Badam	Terminalia catappa	Trees
42	Other	Brittle False Pimpernel	Torenia crustacea	Herbs
43	Other	Tridax procumbens	Tridax Daisy	Herbs
44	Other	Caesar Weed	Urena lobata	Herbs
24	Other	Mung bean	Vigna radiata	Climbers
25	Other	Scrambling Clerodendrum	Volkameria inermis	Climbers
57	Other	Chinese Apple	Ziziphus mauritiana	Shrubs

Sup data Table 2: Animal species observations (Terrestrial)

Sr. No.	Common name	Binomial name	Group
1	African Giant Snail	Lissachatina fulica	Molluska
2	Asian Common Toad	Duttaphrynus melanostictus	Ambhibians
3	Asian House Gecko	Hemidactylus frenatus	Mammals
4	Asian House Shrew	Suncus murinus	Mammals
5	Brown Rat	Rattus norvegicus	Mammals
6	Electric Blue Jumper	Phintella vittata	Spiders
7	Five-striped Palm Squirrel	Funambulus pennantii	Mammals
8	Garden Lizard	Calotes versicolor	Reptiles
9	Golden Jackal	Canis aureus	Mammals
10	Greater Short-nosed Fruit Bat	Cynopterus sphinx	Mammals
11	Green Grass Crab Spiders	Oxytate sp.	Spiders
12	Heavy-bodied jumper	Hyllus semicupreus	Spiders
13	Indian Flying-Fox	Pteropus giganteus	Mammals
14	Indian rat snake	Ptyas mucosa	Reptiles
15	Isopods	Order Isopoda	Crustacean
16	Jumping spider	Asemonea tenuipes	Spiders
17	Keeled Indian mabuya	Eutropis carinata	Reptiles
18	Leatherback Slug	Laevicaulis haroldi	Molluska

19	Lynx spider	Oxyopes sp.	Spiders
20	Millipede	Subfamily Paradoxosomatinae	Myriapoda
21	Rhesus Macaque	Macaca mulatta	Mammals
22	Two-striped jumper	Telamonia dimidiata	Spiders

Sup data Table 3: Bird species observations and Ecology

Sr. No.	Common Name	Scientific Name	Diet	Habitat	Status	Abundance*
1	Ashy prinia	Prinia socialis	IV	NS	LC	++++
2	Asian Green Bee-eater	Merops orientalis	IV	NS	LC	+
3	Asian Koel	Eudynamys scolopaceus	FN	NS	LC	+++
4	Asian Palm Swift	Cypsiurus balasiensis	IV	NS	LC	+++
5	Baya Weaver	Ploceus philippinus	PS	NS	LC	++
6	Black Kite	Milvus migrans	VC	NS	LC	++
7	Black-crowned Night Heron	Nycticorax nycticorax	VC	WT	LC	+
8	Black-headed Gull	Chroicocephalus ridibundus	OM	WT	LC	+
9	Black-headed Ibis	Threskiornis melanocephalus	VC	WT	NT	++
10	Blue-tailed Bee-eater	Merops orientalis	IV	NS	LC	+
11	Cattle Egret	Bubulcus coromandus	IV	WT	LC	++++
12	Chestnut-tailed Starling	Sturnia malabarica	OM	FP	LC	+
13	Common Babbler	Argya caudata	OM	OH	LC	++
14	Common Kingfisher	Alcedo atthis	VC	WT	LC	+
15	Common Myna	Acridotheres tristis	OM	NS	LC	++
16	Common Sandpiper	Actitis hypoleucos	OM	WT	LC	++
17	Common Tailorbird	Orthotomus sutorius	IV	NS	LC	++
18	Garganey	Spatula clypeata	PS	WT	LC	+
19	Glossy Ibis	Plegadis falcinellus	IV	WT	LC	+
20	Gray Heron	Ardea cinerea	VC	WT	LC	+++
21	Great Egret	Ardea alba	IV	WT	LC	+++
22	Greater Coucal	Centropus sinensis	PS	WT	LC	+
23	Greater Flamingo	Phoenicopterus roseus	OM	WT	LC	+++
24	Gull-billed Tern	Gelochelidon nilotica	VC	WT	LC	+
25	House Crow	Corvus splendens	VC	NS	LC	++
26	House Sparrow	Passer domesticus	PS	NS	LC	+
27	Indian Cormorant	Phalacrocorax fuscicollis	VC	WT	LC	++
28	Indian Golden Oriole	Oriolus kundoo	OM	NS	LC	+
29	Indian Pied Starling	Gracupica contra	OM	NS	LC	+++
30	Indian Pond-Heron	Ardeola grayii	OM	NS	LC	++
31	Large-billed Crow	Corvus macrorhynchos	OM	NS	LC	+
32	Lesser Flamingo	Phoeniconaias minor	PS	WT	NT	++

33	Little Cormorant	Microcarbo niger	VC	WT	LC	++
34	Little Egret	Egretta garzetta	IV	WT	LC	+
35	Medium Egret	Ardea intermedia	IV	WT	LC	+++
36	Northern Shoveler	Spatula clypeata	PS	WT	LC	+
37	Oriental Darter	Anhinga melanogaster	VC	WT	NT	+
38	Painted Stork	Mycteria leucocephala	VC	WT	NT	++
39	Purple Sunbird	Cinnyris asiaticus	FN	NS	LC	+
40	Purple-rumped Sunbird	Leptocoma zeylonica	FN	NS	LC	+++
41	Red-vented Bulbul	Pycnonotus cafer	OM	NS	LC	+++
42	Red-whiskered Bulbul	Pycnonotus jocosus	OM	NS	LC	++
43	Rock Pigeon	Columba livia	PS	NS	LC	++
44	Rose-ringed Parakeet	Psittacula krameri	FN	NS	LC	++
45	Scaly-breasted Munia	Lonchura punctulata	PS	NS	LC	+
46	Shikra	Accipiter badius	VC	NS	LC	+
47	Spot-breasted Fantail	Rhipidura albogularis	IV	FP	LC	+
48	Sykes's Warbler	Acrocephalus bistrigiceps	IV	WT	LC	++
49	Whiskered Tern	Chlidonias hybrida	VC	WT	LC	+
50	White-eared Bulbul	Pycnonotus leucotis	OM	NS	LC	+
51	White-throated Kingfisher	Halcyon smyrnensis	VC	NS	LC	++
52	Wood Sandpiper	Tringa glareola	IV	WT	LC	+
53	Zitting Cisticola	Cisticola juncidis	IV	OH	LC	+

- Diet: IV: Invertebrate, FN: Fruit & Nectar, PS: Plant & Seed, VC: Vertebrate & Carrion, OM: Omnivore
- Habitat preference: NS: Non-specialized, WT: Wetland, FP: Forest & Plantation, OH: Open Habitat,
- IUCN status: LC: Least Concern, NT: Near Threatened
- Abundance: Relative abundance based on observation counts during the study period
 +: 1-5 individuals,
 ++: 5-10 individuals,
 +++: 10-20 individuals,
 ++++: More than 20 individuals

Sup data Table 4: Insect diversity (Pollinator species)

Sr. No.	Common Name	Binomial name	Group
1	Indian Black Ant	Camponotus compressus	Ants
2	Arboreal Bicolored Slender Ant	Tetraponera rufonigra	Ants
3	Big-headed Ants	Genus Pheidole	Ants
4	Crematogaster ants	Subgenus Crematogaster	Ants
5	Ghost Ant	Tapinoma melanocephalum	Ants
6	Asian Honey Bee	Apis cerana	Bees
7	Subgenus Seladonia	Seladonia	Bees

8	Cloak-and-Dagger Bees	Genus Thyreus	Bees
9	Stingless bees	Genus Tetragonula	Bees
10	Apis dorsata	Giant Honey Bee	Bees
11	Apis florea	Red Dwarf Honey Bee	Bees
12	Genus Megachile	Leafcutter	Bees
13	Black Reed Bees	Genus Braunsapis	Bees
14	Woodborer Bees	Genus Lithurgus	Bees
15		Subgenus Hoplonomia	Bees
16		Subgenus Zonamegilla	Bees
17	Green Tortoise Beetle	Cassida circumdata	Beetles
18	Cocoa Branch Borer	Olenecamptus bilobus	Beetles
19		Genus Dorcus	Beetles
20	Scarabs	Family Scarabaeidae	Beetles
21	Snout beetle		Beetles
22	Stag Beetles	Subfamily Apoderinae	Beetles
23		Anegleis cardoni	Beetles
24		Oides palleata	Beetles
25	Old World Soapberry Bugs	Genus Leptocoris	Beetles
26	Leaf-footed Bugs	Family Coreidae	Bugs
27	Lace Bugs	Family Tingidae	Bugs
28		Genus Graptostethus	Bugs
29		Genus Halyomorpha	Bugs
30		Genus Leptocorisa	Bugs
31		Genus Spilostethus	Bugs
32	Seed bugs	Oncopeltus nigriceps	Bugs
33	Seed-eating Bugs		Bugs
34		Erthesina acuminata	Bugs
35		Carbula scutellata	Bugs
36		Cylindralcides bubo	Bugs
37	Common Mormon Swallowtail	Papilio polytes	Bugs
38	Lime Swallowtail	Papilio demoleus	Butterflies
39	Lemon Emigrant	Catopsilia pomona	Butterflies
40	Blue Tiger	Tirumala limniace	Butterflies
41	Common Crow Butterfly	Euploea core	Butterflies
42	Common Grass Yellow	Eurema hecabe	Butterflies
43	Lime Blue	Chilades lajus	Butterflies
44	Tailed Jay	Graphium agamemnon	Butterflies
45	Plain Tiger Butterfly	Danaus chrysippus	Butterflies
46	Grey Pansy	Junonia atlites	Butterflies
47	Tawny Coster	Acraea terpsicore	Butterflies
48	Small Salmon Arab	Colotis amata	Butterflies
49	Common Jay	Graphium doson	Butterflies
50	Common Cerulean	Jamides celeno	Butterflies
51	Common Palmfly	Elymnias hypermnestra	Butterflies

52	Lesser Grass Blue	Zizina otis	Butterflies
53	Commander	Moduza procris	Butterflies
54	Black Rajah	Charaxes solon	Butterflies
55	Gram Blue	Euchrysops cnejus	Butterflies
56	Great Eggfly	Hypolimnas bolina	Butterflies
57	Peacock Pansy	Junonia almana	Butterflies
58	Plains Cupid	Luthrodes pandava	Butterflies
59	Common Leopard	Phalanta phalantha	Butterflies
60	Dark Grass Blue	Zizeeria karsandra	Butterflies
61	Common Sailer	Neptis hylas	Butterflies
62	Red Pierrot	Talicauda nyseus	Butterflies
63	Blue Pierrots	Genus Tarucus	Butterflies
64	Common Baron	Euthalia aconthea	Butterflies
65	Common Castor	Ariadne merione	Butterflies
66	Common Hedge Blue	Acytolepis puspa	Butterflies
67	Indian Palm Bob	Suastus gremius	Butterflies
68	Lemon Pansy	Junonia lemonias	Butterflies
69	Brown Awl	Badamia exclamationis	Butterflies
70	Common Gull	Cepora nerissa	Butterflies
71	Indian Wanderer	Pareronia hippia	Butterflies
72	Pale Palm Dart	Telicota colon	Butterflies
73	Tailless Lineblue	Prosotas dubiosa	Butterflies
74	Striped Tiger	Danaus genutia	Butterflies
75	Indian Jezebel	Delias eucharis	Butterflies
76	Small Grass Yellow	Eurema brigitta	Butterflies
77	Indian Cupid	Everes lacturnus	Butterflies
78	Common Awl	Hasora badra	Butterflies
79	Common Banded Awl	Hasora chromus	Butterflies
80	Chestnut Bob	Iambrix salsala	Butterflies
81	Indian Sunbeam	Curetis thetis	Butterflies
82	Junonia iphita	Chocolate Pansy	Butterflies
83	Rice Swift	Borbo cinnara	Butterflies
84	Grass Demon	Udaspes folus	Butterflies
85	Striped Albatross	Appias libythea	Butterflies
86	Blue Pansy	Junonia orithya	Butterflies
87	Bright Babul Blue	Azonus ubaldus	Butterflies
88	Conjoined Swift	Pelopidas conjuncta	Butterflies
89	Dark Cerulean	Jamides bochus	Butterflies
90	Great Mormon	Papilio agenor	Butterflies
91	Psyche	Leptosia nina	Butterflies
92	Malabar Spotted Flat	Celaenorrhinus ambareesa	Butterflies
93	Pointed Ciliate Blue	Anthene lycaenina	Butterflies
94	Small Branded Swift	Pelopidas mathias	Butterflies
95	Straight Swifts	Genus Parnara	Butterflies

96	Tiny Grass Blue	Zizula hylax	Butterflies
97	White Orange Tip	Ixias marianne	Butterflies
98	Yellow Orange Tip	Ixias pyrene	Butterflies
99	Zebra Blue	Leptotes plinius	Butterflies
100	Striped Small Carpenter Bees	Subgenus Ceratinidia	Butterflies
101	Windowed Carpenter	Xylocopa fenestrata	Carpenter Bees
102	Common Bluetail	Ischnura senegalensis	Carpenter Bees
103	Blue Ground Skimmer	Diplacodes trivialis	Dragonflies
104	Wandering Glider	Pantala flavescens	Dragonflies
105	Ruddy Marsh Skimmer	Crocothemis servilia	Dragonflies
106		Tribe Clytrini	Dragonflies
107		Mesembrius bengalensis	Flies
108	Oriental Latrine Fly	Chrysomya megacephala	Flies
109	Long-legged Flies	Family Dolichopodidae	Flies
110	House Flies and Allies	Family Muscidae	Flies
111	Flesh Flies and Satellite Flies	Family Sarcophagidae	Flies
112		Genus Batocera	Flies
113		Genus Eristalinus	Flies
114		Genus Grammicomyia	Flies
115		Genus Odontomyia	Flies
116		Genus Physiphora	Flies
117	Lagoon Flies	Subfamily Exoristinae	Flies
118		Genus Atractomorpha	Flies
119	Family Acrididae	Short-horned Grasshoppers	Grasshoppers
120	Eggplant Horned Planthopper	Leptocentrus taurus	Grasshoppers
121		Genus Neodartus	Hoppers
122	Family Chrysopidae	Green Lacewings	Hoppers
123	Giant Asian Mantises	Genus Hierodula	Lacewings
124	Asian Ant Mantis	Odontomantis planiceps	Mantises
125	Family Chironomidae	Non-biting Midges	Mantises
126	Rose-Myrtle Lappet Moths	Genus Trabala	Midges
127	Oleander Hawkmoth	Daphnis nerii	Moths
128	Pellucid Hawkmoth	Cephonodes hylas	Moths
129	Banyan Tussock Moth	Perina nuda	Moths
130	Castor Semi-Looper	Achaea janata	Moths
131	Bagworm Moths	Family Psychidae	Moths
132	Chrysodeixis	Genus Chrysodeixis	Moths
133		Genus Dysdercus	Moths
134		Chiasmia emersaria	Moths
135		Altha subnotata	Moths
136	Blue-striped Nettle Grub	Parasa lepida	Moths
137		Chabula acamasalis	Moths
138	Citrus Leafminer	Phyllocnistis citrella	Moths
139	Common Hunter Hawkmoth	Theretra clotho	Moths

140	Footman Moth	Nepita conferta	Moths
141		Genus Dysgonia	Moths
142		Genus Helicoverpa	Moths
143		Genus Omiodes	Moths
144		Genus Rhesala	Moths
145		Genus Scopula	Moths
146	Rattlepod Moths	Genus Utetheisa	Moths
147	Brown Tussock Moth	Olene mendosa	Moths
148		Orvasca subnotata	Moths
149	Tasar Silk Moth	Antheraea paphia	Moths
150		Eretmocera impactella	Moths
151	Small Paper Wasps	Genus Ropalidia	Moths
152	Chalcidid Wasps	Family Chalcididae	Wasps
153		Genus Anastatus	Wasps
154		Genus Anomalon	Wasps
155		Genus Cerceris	Wasps
156	Oriental Mud-dauber Wasp	Chalybion bengalense	Wasps
157		Subfamily Campsomerinae	Wasps
158	Typical Weevil Wasps and Allies	Cerceris	Wasps
158		Delta conoideum	Wasps

References:

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